

Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) and Rational Drug Design for Some Antineoplastic Thalidomide and Glutarimide Derivatives.

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Quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) of 38 thalidomide and glutarimide derivatives, earlier synthesized and evaluated as possible antineoplastic agents against Ehrlich ascites carcinoma, has been determined with the help of Free-Wilson's Mathematical Model which results in the prediction and rational designing of the most potent member in this class of compounds.

THE Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship (QSAR) still an emerging field can in practical terms optimize and generate new leads in the field of drug design¹. Any structural change, in the biologically active molecule, effects the biological activity which can be interpreted in terms of the changes caused in the lipophilic, electronic and steric character of the molecule. Besides these factors, there are many other factors, like barrier passage, metabolism intervening the pathway from drug administration to the attainment of desired biophase concentration at the active site, which can neither be predicted, nor visualised. The regression analysis, a branch of statistics, has been successfully exploited through Hansch-Fujita's free energy related $\rho - \sigma - \pi$ analysis² and through Free-Wilson's additivity model³, in which the constant term in the equation accounts for the contribution of the factors unexplained in the equation or for the intrinsic activity. In addition to these, a theoretical quantum chemical approach⁴⁻⁷, which involves the use of molecular orbital indices and the geometry of the molecule⁴⁻⁷ in space, has also been applied.

Details of synthesis and evaluation of antineoplastic activities of 38 thalidomide and glutarimide derivatives against Ehrlich ascites carcinoma have been reported by the present authors in two earlier communications^{8, 9}.

In the present case of quantitative structure-activity relationship, Free-Wilson's Mathematical Model has been utilized. For this model the parent structure (I) has been selected.

A linear equation has been constructed representing each compound and observation, where the substituents R_1, R_2, R_3 at positions 2, 3, 6 are denoted by a, b, c. The activity contribution of the substituent groups at a particular position to the total activity are indicated by brackets and the contribution of the parent structure is expressed by μ . Then,

Biological response = μ + sum of the individual group contributions

$$= \mu + \Sigma \text{group contributions.}$$

As biological response parameters, cell inhibition, tumor weight inhibition, log cell inhibition and log tumor weight inhibition have been utilized. The reason for using the log of biological responses as activity parameter is that these are often considered to be free energy related and as such possess an additive character¹⁰⁻¹³. Based on these guidelines, 38 simultaneous equations with 22 unknowns representing 38 compounds can be constructed. Some specimen equations are cited below :

	Percent cell inhibition	Percent tumor weight inhibition	Log (percent cell inhibition)	Log (percent tumor weight inhibition)
(1) $a[H] + b[H] + c[H] + \mu = 42.25$	16.67	16.67	1.6258	1.2219
(2) $a[H] + b[C_6H_5] + c[CH_3] + \mu = 97.92$	85.91	85.91	1.9909	1.9341
(3) $a[H] + b[C_6H_5] + c[C_2H_5] + \mu = 95.28$	86.51	86.51	1.9790	1.9371
⋮				
(38) $a[o\text{-Sulfobenzoicimido}] + b[H] + c[H] + \mu = 57.34$	48.58	48.58	1.7585	1.6864

Furthermore, the imposition of symmetry restriction in accordance with the Frec-Wilson's Model leads to 3 more following equations, the number of variables remaining same :

The matrix representation of these 41 equations with 22 variables is given in Table 1.

Least square solution of this set of simultaneous equations with the help of a IBM 1130 computer gives the individual contribution of each substituent group, that of the parent structure (μ), calculated total activity of each compound and standard deviations (σ). These calculated activities were then plotted against the observed biological activities when most of the points were near the 45° line indicating a relatively good correlation between the two sets of values. Moreover, multiple correlation coefficients (R) and variance ratios ($F_{k,n}$) were computed from these data^{14,15}. The observed and calculated biological activities of the compounds along with the standard deviations, multiple

correlation coefficients and variance ratios are recorded in Table 1. The individual contribution of each substituent is recorded in Table 2.

Conclusion : It will be evident from these results that certain groups like methyl at position '6' (i.e. x_6), *n*-butyl at position 6 (i.e. x_9), *n*-hexyl at position 6 (i.e. x_{11}), phenyl at position 6 (i.e. x_{12}), *p*-methoxy phenyl at position 3 (i.e. x_{15}) behave anomalously, whereas contributions of some groups like phenyl at position 3 (i.e. x_3), *n*-propyl at position 6 (i.e. x_8), benzyl at position 6 (i.e. x_{13}), phthalimido at position 2 (i.e. x_{16}), 4'-nitrophthalimido at position 2 (i.e. x_{17}), *p*-toluenesulfonamido at position 2 (i.e. x_{21}) etc. are quite significant. Certain functions like H at positions 3 and 6 (i.e. x_2 and x_3), *n*-pentyl at position 6 (i.e. x_{10}), cyclohexyl at position 6 (i.e. x_{14}), *o*-sulfobenzoic imido at position 2 (i.e. x_{19}) have negative contributions to the total activity. It will be evident from this analysis that a glutarimide derivative having a benzene sulfonamido group at position 2, a phenyl group at position 3, and a *n*-propyl group at position 6 is likely to be most potent in this class of compounds. The multiple correlation coefficient values show improvement when log of the biological parameters are taken into consideration. The $F(k, n)$ values indicate a 75% level of significance for run 1, 2 and 4, and 90% level for run 3. Lastly, it should be pointed out that further reduction of the number of independent variables with the help of equations 39 to 41, and rejection of some anomalously behaving variables in future computational work are likely to improve the significance level appreciably.

TABLE 2—CONTRIBUTION OF INDIVIDUAL SUBSTITUENT AND THE PARENT MOIETY

No. of Variables	Percent cell inhibition	Percent tumor weight inhibition	log (percent cell inhibition)	log (percent tumor weight inhibition)
x_1	-12.170071	20.905143	-0.065111439	-0.24517768
x_2	-14.908537	-27.943336	-0.11149653	-0.30273032
x_3	-2.4716046	-7.013676	0.0022842237	-0.053684196
x_4	71.800210	72.589842	1.8001236	1.8234921
x_5	29.547533	23.870103	0.21363188	0.25588229
x_6	4.4012277	-11.275368	0.030159205	-0.065146715
x_7	11.614561	3.8356312	0.084425872	0.038786617
x_8	21.244561	16.009631	0.13845920	0.11248661
x_9	-9.9584388	16.036964	-0.085174127	0.11655328
x_{10}	-10.847105	-3.1990353	-0.089274127	-0.0057467156
x_{11}	-11.139605	6.5846313	-0.092065722	0.058590784
x_{12}	11.220894	-7.0520353	0.089425872	-0.13754671
x_{13}	15.439561	11.897964	0.10409253	0.098286618
x_{14}	-20.023772	-11.462035	-0.15697412	-0.056846715
x_{15}	-2.7121664	26.427903	-0.012938119	0.28903229
x_{16}	17.103998	19.522196	0.15067697	0.26243493
x_{17}	42.550931	55.894862	0.29568863	0.50352242
x_{18}	6.1304319	33.550863	-0.02786360	0.36163493
x_{19}	-48.8100.68	-3.4551373	-0.94191136	0.066022426
x_{20}	45.579931	62.424862	0.30908862	0.53292242
x_{21}	30.029931	50.814862	0.23568863	0.47932242
x_{22}	2.9199315	11.004862	-0.67588631	0.21932242

A. U. DE & D. PAL : QUANTITATIVE STRUCTURE-ACTIVITY RELATIONSHIP (QSAR) ETC.

Table 1. MATRIX REPRESENTATION OF THE SIMULTANEOUS EQUATIONS ALONG WITH THE STANDARD DEVIATIONS, MULTIPLE CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS AND VARIANCE RATIOS

No.	x ₁	x ₂	x ₃	x ₄	x ₅	x ₆	x ₇	x ₈	x ₉	x ₁₀	x ₁₁	x ₁₂	x ₁₃	x ₁₄	x ₁₅	x ₁₆	x ₁₇	x ₁₈	x ₁₉	x ₂₀	x ₂₁	x ₂₂	Run (1) Percent cell inhibition		Run (2) Percent tumor weight inhibition		Run (3) Log(Percent cell inhibition)		Run (4) Log(Percent tumor weight inhibition)	
																							obs.	calcd	obs.	calcd	obs.	calcd	obs.	calcd
1	1	1	1	1																			42.25	42.249	16.67	16.669	1.6578	1.625	1.2219	1.221
2	1		1	1	1																		97.92	86.706	85.91	68.483	1.9709	1.950	1.9341	1.780
3	1		1	1	1	1																	95.28	93.578	86.51	64.279	1.9790	1.978	1.9371	1.769
4	1		1	1	1	1	1																93.71	100.792	82.01	79.390	1.9717	2.033	1.9139	1.872
5	1		1	1	1	1	1	1															96.93	110.422	98.37	91.564	1.9864	2.087	1.9929	1.946
6	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1														96.12	79.219	98.64	91.591	1.9828	1.863	1.9941	1.950
7	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1													83.83	78.330	71.43	72.355	1.9234	1.859	1.8539	1.828
8	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1												61.56	78.038	71.43	82.139	1.7893	1.856	1.8539	1.892
9	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1											90.36	100.398	14.28	68.502	1.9560	2.038	1.1548	1.696
10	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1										100.00	104.617	80.64	87.452	2.0000	2.052	1.9065	1.932
11	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1									85.55	69.153	80.64	64.092	1.9323	1.791	1.9065	1.777
12	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1								33.39	54.446	30.00	71.041	1.5236	1.724	1.4771	1.813
13	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1							44.96	61.319	60.00	66.837	1.6528	1.752	1.7782	1.802
14	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1						63.03	68.532	97.33	81.948	1.7995	1.806	1.9882	1.906
15	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1					100.00	78.162	100.00	94.122	2.0000	1.860	2.0000	1.979
16	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1				28.90	46.959	92.31	94.149	1.4548	1.636	1.9652	1.983
17	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			76.48	46.070	92.31	74.913	1.8836	1.632	1.9652	1.861
18	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			62.94	45.778	91.77	84.697	1.7990	1.630	1.9627	1.925
19	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			76.08	68.138	84.00	71.060	1.8813	1.811	1.9243	1.729
20	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			66.41	72.357	88.89	90.010	1.8223	1.826	1.9488	1.965
21	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			26.87	36.894	58.82	66.650	1.4292	1.565	1.7695	1.810
22	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			45.20	71.524	60.00	57.097	1.6551	1.841	1.7782	1.729
23	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			93.05	78.396	37.50	52.893	1.9687	1.869	1.5740	1.718
24	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			98.20	85.610	50.00	68.004	1.9921	1.923	1.6990	1.821
25	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			86.90	95.240	67.50	80.178	1.9390	1.977	1.8293	1.895
26	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			65.60	64.037	75.00	80.205	1.8169	1.754	1.8751	1.899
27	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			27.24	63.148	44.50	60.969	1.4352	1.750	1.6484	1.777
28	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			88.34	62.856	95.10	70.753	1.9928	1.747	1.9782	1.841
29	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			87.31	85.216	98.40	57.116	1.9410	1.928	1.9930	1.645
30	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			100.00	89.435	84.00	76.066	2.0000	1.943	1.9243	1.881
31	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			47.69	53.971	43.99	52.706	1.6776	1.682	1.6382	1.726
32	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			96.97	96.970	93.47	93.470	1.9866	1.986	1.9706	1.970
33	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			96.71	68.550	91.84	71.126	1.9854	1.638	1.9630	1.828
34	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			15.72	51.882	64.07	84.781	1.1965	1.543	1.8067	1.940
35	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			5.61	5.610	34.120	34.120	0.7490	0.748	1.5331	1.533
36	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			100.00	100.000	100.000	100.000	2.0000	1.999	2.0000	2.000
37	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			84.45	84.450	88.390	88.390	1.9266	1.926	1.9464	1.946
38	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			57.34	57.340	48.580	48.580	1.7585	1.758	1.6864	1.686
39	21																						0.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.0000	0.000	0.0000	0.000
40	18																						0.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.0000	0.000	0.0000	0.000
41	10																						0.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.0000	0.000	0.0000	0.000

Where, x₁ = a [H], x₂ = b [H], x₃ = o [H], x₄ = H, x₅ = b [C₆H₅], x₆ = o [CH₃], x₇ = c [C₆H₅], x₈ = o [p-C₆H₄], x₉ = c [p-C₆H₄], x₁₀ = o [p-C₆H₄], x₁₁ = o [p-C₆H₄], x₁₂ = o [C₆H₅], x₁₃ = o [C₆H₅CH₂], x₁₄ = o [cyclohexyl], x₁₅ = b [p-C₆H₄OC₆H₅], x₁₆ = a [phthalimido], x₁₇ = a [4'-nitro phthalimido], x₁₈ = a [3'-nitro phthalimido], x₁₉ = a [p-mulfo benzoicimido], x₂₀ = a [benzenesulfonimido], x₂₁ = a [p-toluensulfonimido], x₂₂ = a [p-acetamidobenzenesulfonimido].

For run (1): σ = 16.211886, R = 0.866; run (2): σ = 16.518724, R = 0.835; run (3): σ = 0.134714, R = 0.967; run (4): σ = 0.138696, R = 0.963.
 F₀₁₁₄ = 1.38 F₁₆₂₁ = 1.41 F₀₁₁₄ = 1.96 F₁₆₂₁ = 1.36

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